

Mechanical Behavior of Circular Composite Springs with Extended Flat Contact Surfaces

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SUMMARY : Theoretical expressions based on the principle of minimum potential energy are presented which describe the stiffness and strain distributions of circular composite rings with extended flat contact surfaces subject to uniform-end-shortening. Comparison studies of the results obtained from the analytical models are made with experimental data, and the results are found to be in good agreement. The semi-included angle of the flat contact surface is a vital parameter to spring stiffness and strain distributions of the composite ring. Strain-free locations are found on both the inner and outer surfaces of the shell. These strain-free locations are of great potential to the future development of the composite springs, as they can be used to facilitate attachment of additional accessories or discontinuities, such as holes or fitments.

KEYWORDS : spring stiffness, strain distributions, extended flat contact surfaces, minimum potential energy, uniform-end-shortening, strain-free locations.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced plastic composite materials are ideal for many engineering and structural applications owing to their attractive physical properties. Current interest in reducing the weight of motor vehicles has brought numerous new applications for fibre reinforced composites. Light car bodies require simpler engines and transmissions both of which can therefore be lighter and more efficient on fuel economy. Composite springs are being recognized as a viable replacement for steel springs in automotive suspension applications because of its high specific strain energy storage capability. Further advantages of composite springs accrue from the ability to design and fabricate a spring having adjustable spring rate and non-linear characteristic.

The review made by Scowen [1] provides useful information concerning the material requirements for product development and the transport applications of composite materials. Recognizing the need for non-linear spring response and the composite spring must function in the same vertical deflection mode and within the same space as a steel coil spring, the 'Slucated Spring' was introduced and test data showed that it is a very promising concept [2]. The non-linearity was incorporated into the performance by the contact of the radial sections

of the springs resulting in a highly non-linear increase in spring stiffness beyond the initial linear deflection region.

The composite elliptic springs of Mallick [3] represents another generation of composite spring development that is not purely limited to simply replacing the spring material but involves a change in geometry as well. Several elliptic spring elements constructed from unidirectional E-glass fibre reinforced epoxy tapes were mounted in series and tested in quasi-static compression. Failure analysis and the joining problems of the spring elements were investigated.

The mechanical behavior of woven fabric composite cylindrical springs with mid-plane symmetry has been investigated by So [4]. The theory was developed based on a linear-elastic assumption and the stress-strain distributions around the ring were evaluated. Small deformations were accurately predicted. The objective of this work is to study the function of a composite spring as an energy storage device. Of particular interest is the mechanical behavior of circular composite springs with extended flat contact surfaces subject to uniform-end-shortening loading configuration.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The mid-plane symmetric and thin-walled composite spring made of E-glass woven fabric-epoxy is shown in Fig.1. Both the upper and lower flat contact surfaces of the composite spring are bonded to mild steel rigid fasteners such that strain energy is mainly stored in the flexible arm when under loading. Since the rigidity of the sandwiched portion of the composite spring is very large, the uniformly distributed load can be approximated by an resultant force P acting on the middle of the sandwiched flat surface as shown in Fig.1.

Spring stiffness :-

In view of symmetry, only one half of a composite ring of mid-plane radius R need be considered, as shown in Fig.2. The total strain energy of the composite ring [4] is

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \frac{(D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}{|D|} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\pi - \alpha_1} M_{AB}^2 R d\theta \\
 &= \frac{(D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}{|D|} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\pi - \alpha_1} \left(M_B - \frac{PR \sin \theta}{2} \right)^2 R d\theta \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where D_{ij} = flexural stiffness of a laminate

$|D|$ = determinant of flexural stiffness matrix

By Castigliano's Second Theorem, the bending moment, M_{AB} , for any cross-section of a slender ring under uniaxial load P is

$$M_{AB} = \frac{PR \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{PR \sin \theta}{2} \quad (2)$$

The vertical deflection of the spring is

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \frac{\partial U}{\partial P} = 2 \frac{(D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}{|D|} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\pi - \alpha_1} M_{AB} \frac{\partial M_{AB}}{\partial P} R d\theta \\
 &= 2 \frac{(D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}{|D|} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\pi - \alpha_1} \left(\frac{PR \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{PR \sin \theta}{2} \right) \left(\frac{R \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{P \sin \theta}{2} \right) R d\theta \\
 &= \frac{PR^3 (D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}{|D|} \lambda_1
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $\lambda_1 = \frac{\sin 2\alpha_1}{4} + \frac{\pi - 2\alpha_1}{4} - \frac{2 \cos^2 \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1}$

The spring stiffness is

$$\begin{aligned}
 K &= \frac{PL}{V} = \frac{L|D|}{R^3 (D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2) \lambda_1} \\
 &= \frac{8L|D|}{(2R_o + H)^3 (D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2) \lambda_1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

since $R = R_o + H/2$. Where R_o , H and L are the internal radius, thickness and width of the ring respectively.

For a specially orthotropic laminate having symmetric and balanced lay-up of identical laminae

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{|D|}{D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2} &= \frac{H^3}{12} E_{11}, \\
 \text{hence } K &= \frac{2LH^3 E_{11}}{3(2R_o + H)^3 \lambda_1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where E_{11} is the Young's modulus in the principal direction 1.

Strain distributions :-

Since the two flat portions BC and AD are bonded to mild steel rigid fasteners, failure is unlikely to be occurred on the flat contact surfaces. It is realistic to consider the strain distributions in the portion AB only. The mid-plane strains and curvature equations are

$$[\varepsilon^o] = \frac{1}{H} [S] [N] = \frac{1}{H} [Q]^{-1} [N] \quad (6)$$

$$[\kappa] = \frac{12}{H^3} [S] [M] = \frac{12}{H^3} [Q]^{-1} [M] \quad (7)$$

[N] and [M] are stress and moment resultants respectively.

[Q] and [S] are lamina stiffness matrix and compliance matrix respectively.

$$\text{where } [S] = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and } S_{11} = \frac{1}{E_{11}}, \quad S_{22} = \frac{1}{E_{22}}, \quad S_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}},$$

$$S_{12} = \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} = \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_{22}}$$

E_{22} = Young's modulus in principal direction 2

G_{12} = shear modulus with reference to the principal axes.

ν_{12}, ν_{21} = major and minor Poisson's ratio respectively.

For properties in 1 and 2 directions are the same, i.e., $E_{11} = E_{22}$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21}$, $Q_{11} = Q_{22} = E_{11} / (1 - \nu_{12}^2)$ and $Q_{12} = \nu_{12} Q_{11}$. Therefore

$$[\varepsilon^o] = \frac{1}{H} \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ -P \sin \theta / 2 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{P \sin \theta}{2HE_{11}} \begin{Bmatrix} \nu_{12} \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$[\kappa] = \frac{12}{H^3} \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{PR \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{PR \sin \theta}{2} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$= \frac{12}{E_{11}H^3} \left(\frac{PR \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{PR \sin \theta}{2} \right) \begin{Bmatrix} -\nu_{12} \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

For a point at a distance z from the neutral axis, the strain written in terms of mid-plane strains and changes in mid-plane curvatures is

$$[\varepsilon] = [\varepsilon^o] + z[\kappa] = \left\{ \frac{-P \sin \theta}{2HE_{11}} + \frac{12zPR}{H^3E_{11}} \left(\frac{\cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{\sin \theta}{2} \right) \right\} \begin{Bmatrix} -\nu_{12} \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

Five specimens were manufactured by circumferential winding of E-glass woven cloth impregnated with epoxy resin on a mandrel. Loss on ignition test [5] was performed for the determination of glass content. Tensile tests were performed on rectangular strips of unreinforced epoxy resin according to the standards set by ASTM [6], to determine the engineering properties of the resin. The elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the epoxy were found as 2.93GPa and 0.38 respectively. The elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the fibres were taken to be 75.9GPa and 0.22 respectively [7]. A modified 'rule of mixtures' [7] was used as a mathematical model to predict the engineering properties of the composite springs.

Experimental set-up for the quasi-static compression test is schematically shown in Fig.3. The flat contact surfaces of the composite spring were sandwiched and bonded by two 15mm thick mild steel plates. Some specimens were compressed until failure and Table 1 shows the value of the failure loads. Electrical resistance foil strain gauges were mounted on the inside and outside surfaces of spring No.5 to measure the strain distributions in the circumferential direction of the circular portion at various locations in uniaxial compression test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental and theoretical spring rates are tabulated in Table 1 for comparison purpose. In general, the spring stiffness is over-estimated by the theoretical model. The discrepancies could be due to the method of fabrication, whereas the specimens contained unintentional random geometric imperfections. Failure of the specimens was initiated by splitting of layers at the corners of the composite springs with cracks propagation as the load increased until final crashing at the circular arms. Eqn 5 indicates that the spring stiffness is proportional to a spring parameter $(E_{11}LH^3)/((2R_o+H)^3)$ and is a function of the parameter λ_1 or the semi-included angle α_1 . Variations of $1/\lambda_1$ with α_1 are depicted in Fig.4, it can be seen that the spring stiffness is highly dependent on the length of the extended flat contact surface. In other word, one of the most effective ways to adjust the spring stiffness is to alter the length or the semi-included angle of the extended flat contact surface. For the circumferential strain distributions, basically the general trends for the experimental results are consistent with the theoretical predictions and the discrepancies are attributed to the approximation of elastic properties. As can be seen from Figs.5 and 6 that for both the theoretical and experimental results, zero strain locations were observed. Theoretically, all strain terms will be zero when

$$\left\{ \frac{-P \sin \theta}{2HE_{11}} + \frac{12zPR}{H^3E_{11}} \left(\frac{\cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} - \frac{\sin \theta}{2} \right) \right\} = 0$$

$$\text{Let } \frac{2 \cos \alpha_1}{\pi - 2\alpha_1} = \lambda, \text{ thus the equation becomes } \left\{ \frac{-P \sin \theta}{2HE_{11}} + \frac{6zPR}{H^3E_{11}} (\lambda - \sin \theta) \right\} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \theta = \sin^{-1} \frac{12zR\lambda}{12zR + H^2} \approx \sin^{-1} \lambda, \text{ since } 12zR \text{ is much greater than } H^2.$$

Variations of $(\lambda \sin \theta)$ with respect to the semi-included angle α_1 of the extended flat contact surface are tabulated in Table 2. The circumferential strain distributions are very sensitive to the variation of the length of the extended flat contact surfaces. The strain-free position is load independent but related to the semi-included angle α_1 as far as elastic analysis is concerned.

CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical analysis of the specially orthotropic composite spring with extended flat contact surfaces based on the principle of minimum potential energy has been presented and is validated by experimental data when the spring is subjected to uniform-end-shortening loading. Adjustable spring rate can be achieved by manipulating the length of the extended flat contact surfaces of the spring elements. Strain distributions indicated the existence of load-independent positions on both the outer and inner surfaces of the spring. These strain-free locations are of great interest for the development of the composite spring.

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Fig. 1: Composite ring under equivalent loading conditions

Fig. 2: Forces and moments per unit width acting on one half of a composite ring

Fig. 3: Experimental setup for the quasi static compression test

Fig. 4: Variations of $1/\lambda_1$ with the semi-included angle α_1 of the extended flat contact surface

Fig. 5: Comparison of hoop strain distributions for the outer surface

Fig. 6: Comparison of hoop strain distributions for the inner surface

Table 1: Compression test data for composite springs subject to uniform-end-shortening

Specimen No.	* Thickness H	Width L	Volume fraction	Initial spring stiffness		Fracture load (N)
	(mm)	(mm)		exp. (N/mm)	theo. (N/mm)	
1	0.53	50.80	0.2554	1.07	1.28	---
2	2.67	49.56	0.3202	167.06	179.76	1580
3	3.05	55.90	0.3213	257.38	300.09	---
4	3.41	62.50	0.3503	488.74	497.86	1896
5	3.43	62.50	0.3503	412.55	506.42	1930

* Nominal thickness of circular arm portion

All data are based on $R_O = 57\text{mm}$, $\alpha_1 = 26.5^\circ$

Table 2: Variations of $(\lambda - \sin \theta)$ with respect to the semi-included angle α_1 of the extended flat contact surface

$\theta \backslash \alpha_1$	10°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°
10°	0.532	0.363	0.205	0.063	-0.061	-0.161	-0.234	-0.279	-0.295
20°		0.427	0.269	0.126	0.003	-0.097	-0.171	-0.216	-0.231
30°			0.327	0.184	0.061	-0.039	-0.113	-0.158	-0.173
40°				0.235	0.112	0.012	-0.062	-0.107	-0.122
50°					0.155	0.055	-0.019	-0.064	-0.079